

A UNIQUE CRITERION FOR DESCRIBING FAILURE OF FOAM CORE SANDWICH MATERIALS - A DESIGN ENGINEERING PERSPECTIVE

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SUMMARY

The Tsai-Wu criterion in its simplified or modified form could be quite suitable to describe the failure of most of the commercially available cellular foams and for proper dimensioning of foam core sandwich materials. Using this criterion for closed cell polyvinylchloride foams (PVC) has already shown good agreement with the experimental results [1]. However, there are hardly studies that describe the correctness of applying this criterion for other important classifications of commercially available cellular foams. This paper describes not only the applicability of a simplified Tsai-Wu criterion for other important foam core materials such as Polyurethane (PUR) and Polymethacrylimide (PMI), but also its extensibility to sandwich materials. One of the key aspects of this work is to provide solutions for dimensioning sandwich materials that incorporate less experimental cost without compromising the light weight advantage.

Keywords: Failure criteria, Design, Polymer foams, Sandwich, Experiments

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are usually made up of two thin and stiff face sheets separated by a thick low density core material. Using polymer foams as a sandwich core has several advantages; they are less expensive as compared to honeycomb core, they are easy to manufacture as well as to bond to other materials [2]. In addition to this, cellular foams offer high thermal insulation and acoustical damping. In recent years, there is an increased interest of using these materials in the transportation sector (e.g. trains, trucks, aircrafts, automobile and ships), in civil engineering applications and even in machine tool manufacturing [3] in order to improve the acceleration and damping properties of the mobile machine parts. Therefore, understanding the failure mechanisms and choosing an appropriate failure criterion are indispensable for proper dimensioning of sandwich materials with foam core under complex loading conditions.

Problem, State-of-the-art

Abrate has summarized various criteria for describing the yielding or failure of cellular foams [4]. Most of these criteria follow a phenomenological approach, meaning that the

criterion is developed so as best fit the experimental data. More than 45 criteria have been described in literature [4]. In addition, several new criteria have been developed in the recent past to describe the failure envelope of such materials precisely. The type and the amount of experiments to be performed often vary from criterion to criterion, which incorporates additional cost and time. Also, it usually demands additional infrastructure and expertise. The Tsai-Wu criterion is widely used for composite materials that are highly anisotropic and have very different strength in compression and tension. Almost all well established commercial finite element programs and even some CAD/FEM-Systems such as Pro/Engineer[®] Mechanical provide Tsai-Wu criteria for predicting failure. Hence it would make sense, instead of developing new failure models/criteria, to check the applicability of this criterion for cellular core materials in general. This would save an enormous amount of research and development work, which in-turn may enhance the applicability of sandwich materials in general engineering applications.

Scope of this work

This paper describes the applicability of Tsai-Wu criterion for foam core materials in general and its extensibility to sandwich materials. To realize this goal, a theoretical background is first established with the aim of reducing the overall experimental cost. The established theory is then validated with the help of two completely dissimilar classes of foam materials; PMI and PUR. PMI is a high performance foam, which is commonly used in aerospace and aeronautical applications, high speed trains, medical technology etc., as an important load carrying element. Whereas, PUR foams are often used in the mechanical engineering industry as a “secondary foam”. The applications include load uncritical areas in shipbuilding, refrigerated trucks, special purpose vehicles etc. The validation for PMI foams is realized in this work by comparing the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion with the newly developed 3-D Rohacell[®] failure criterion and the experiments performed as given in these literatures [5,6]. The details regarding the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion is given in the following paragraph. The validation of PUR foam is realized based on the experiments performed at the Chair and Institute for Engineering Design (IKT).

THEORITICAL BACKGROUND

Stephan W. Tsai and Edward M. Wu have published [7] an operationally simple strength criterion for anisotropic materials. The basic assumption of this strength criteria is that there exists a failure surface in the stress space in the following scalar form, where $i,j,k = 1,2,\dots,6$.

$$f(\sigma_k) = F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

The expanded form of this criterion can be given as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & F_1 \sigma_1 + F_2 \sigma_2 + F_3 \sigma_3 + F_4 \sigma_4 + F_5 \sigma_5 + F_6 \sigma_6 \\ & + F_{11} \sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + 2F_{13} \sigma_1 \sigma_3 + 2F_{14} \sigma_1 \sigma_{12} + 2F_{15} \sigma_1 \sigma_{23} + 2F_{16} \sigma_1 \sigma_{13} \\ & + F_{22} \sigma_2^2 + 2F_{23} \sigma_2 \sigma_3 + 2F_{24} \sigma_2 \sigma_4 + 2F_{25} \sigma_2 \sigma_5 + 2F_{26} \sigma_2 \sigma_6 \\ & + F_{33} \sigma_3^2 + 2F_{34} \sigma_3 \sigma_4 + 2F_{35} \sigma_3 \sigma_5 + 2F_{36} \sigma_3 \sigma_6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + F_{44}\sigma_{12}^2 + 2F_{45}\sigma_4\sigma_5 + 2F_{46}\sigma_4\sigma_6 \\
& + F_{55}\sigma_5^2 + 2F_{56}\sigma_5\sigma_6 \\
& + F_{66}\sigma_6^2 = 1
\end{aligned} \tag{Eq. 2}$$

where $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ can be considered as the normal stress components and $\sigma_4, \sigma_5, \sigma_6$ can be considered as shear stress components in a 3-D stress space. The total number of independent strength components or unknown factors that has to be experimentally determined are 6 and 21 for F_i and F_{ij} respectively. Additionally, in order to make this failure surface meaningful, a stability criterion must be satisfied as given below:

$$F_{ii}F_{jj} - F_{ij}^2 \geq 0 \tag{Eq. 3}$$

Deduction of strength components for cellular foams

The aim of this part of the work is to reduce the number of unknown factors (6+21) in to a reliable, handful number of components that can be experimentally determined with ease. In order to apply this criterion for cellular foams, the relationship between the common engineering strength constants and the strength components of Eq. 2 must be established. This can be done as follows:

By substituting $i=1$ in Eq. 1, we get:

$$F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + F_1\sigma_1 = 1 \tag{Eq. 4}$$

In order to determine two unknowns in this equation, uni-axial tests of axis 1 with pure tension and compression can be carried out. Hence F_{11} and F_1 are determined. Then we get:

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{F_{1d}F_{1t}}; F_1 = \frac{1}{F_{1t}} - \frac{1}{F_{1d}} \tag{Eq. 5}$$

Where F_{1d} is the compressive strength and F_{1t} is the tensile strength of the considered polymer foam. Since most of the polymer foams available in the market have different strength in tension and compression, but possess ‘‘similar’’ properties in axes 2 and 3, one can assume that $i=1=2=3$; there by making the following conclusion. The independent strength components $F_1, F_2, F_3, F_{11}, F_{22}$ and F_{33} can be described as a pure function of compressive and tensile strength of the polymer foams in the 1st axis. Similarly, the independent strength components that correspond to the shear stresses in Eq. 2 can be determined for instance by substituting $i=4$ in Eq. 1. We get:

$$F_{44} = \frac{1}{S^+S^-}; F_4 = \frac{1}{S^+} - \frac{1}{S^-} \tag{Eq. 6}$$

Where S^+ and S^- are the pure positive and negative shear strength of polymer foams on the 1-2 plane respectively. It can be assumed that for most of the commercially available polymer foams, the difference in the positive and negative shear strength values are quite negligible. Therefore we get:

$$F_4 = 0; S^+ = S^- = S \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

With an additional assumption that polymer foams have “similar” properties in axes 2 and 3; we can write $i=4=5=6$. Therefore we get:

$$F_4 = F_5 = F_6 = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

and F_{44}, F_{55} and F_{66} can be described as a function of the shear strength on the 1-2 plane. The remaining unknowns that has to be yet determined in Eq. 2 are the interactive components F_{ij} , where $i \neq j$. For the determination of these interactive components, simple uni-axial or pure shear tests will not be sufficient [7]. There are a infinite number of ways to determine these constants. Usually biaxial tests or complex shaped specimens could be used to determine these constants, which of course will increase the experimental effort. One effective way to solve this problem is by making the following popular assumption as suggested in literatures [8,9]. Here it is assumed that the interactive component F_{12} can be written as a function of F_{11} and F_{22} and is given by:

$$F_{12} = \frac{-1}{2} \sqrt{F_{11} F_{22}} \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

The validation of this assumption is justified in the following way. Firstly, this assumption satisfies the stability condition (Eq. 3) and secondly, this assumption proves to be quite satisfactory for other composite materials [9]. Hence F_{12} is considered here as a pure function of compressive and tensile strengths of polymer foams. This idea can be generalized and extended to all other interactive components of Eq. 2. Hence each interactive component F_{ij} where $i \neq j$, can be written as a function of shear strength and compressive strength or compressive strength and tensile strength or tensile strength and shear strength of the foam core.

The 3-D Tsai-Wu failure criterion that incorporates all the above defined assumptions is referred in this paper as the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion. This criterion requires merely three engineering strength constants to describe the failure envelope of foam core materials under multi-axial loading conditions. This criterion can be written for a bi-axial stress state as follows:

$$\frac{1}{F_{1d} F_{1z}} (\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) + \left(\frac{1}{F_{1z}} - \frac{1}{F_{1d}} \right) (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{F_{1z} F_{1d}} + \frac{\tau^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

The shear stress term σ_4 of Eq. 2 is replaced in the above equation by τ , as such a description is popular and convenient to identify shear stresses in engineering literatures.

Extensibility of simplified Tsai-Wu Criterion for foam core sandwich materials

The goal of this part of the work is to extend the applicability of *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion, so that dimensioning of sandwich materials can be made at less experimental cost. This creates a need for proper selection of experiments, that gives the necessary strength as well as stiffness information of sandwich materials. Therefore, the experiments are to be chosen in such a way that:

- the sandwich element is considered as a whole component for experimentation. This will help avoiding preparation of expensive test specimens of special shapes.
- they consider the strength of foam material as well as the interface adhesive strength between the foam core and the face sheet. The advantage of such a consideration is that, it simplifies the modelling approach in a FEM-Program. One can simply neglect the modelling of adhesive layer, if any.
- only the important load case relevant to the practical applications is considered for validation.

Four experiments and their working principles as shown in Figure 1, can be performed to realize the goal. The strength data, that can be obtained by performing these experiments are also indicated in this figure.

Figure 1: Choice of Testing

The simplest of them is the designing of compressive testing fixture (DIN 53291 or ASTM C365) from which the compressive strength of the foam core can be determined. With the help of tensile testing fixture (DIN 53292 or ASTM C297), it is possible to calculate the strength of the core as well as the interface face-core adhesive strength. Similarly shear testing fixture (DIN 53294 or ASTM C273) could be used to determine the shear strength of the core as well as the interface face-core adhesive strength. However it shall be noted that pure shear strength of the core cannot be obtained by this shear testing fixture as the specimens are under biaxial stress state. Since the sandwich materials are basically used to improve the flexural rigidity of the structure, bending (DIN 53293) remains as the most significant and practically relevant load case of all.

Another important advantage is that it can be used to study the failure mechanisms of sandwich materials.

Both tests (shear and bending) can be used to determine the shear strength of foam core materials. Therefore performing both of them may be redundant, if core shear strength is the parameter of interest. In any case, bending tests must be performed in order to verify the theory as well as to eliminate any manufacturing uncertainties in the sandwich composition. In some cases, manufacturers offer sandwich materials in which a low density PUR foam core is foamed in-situ, thus giving an integrated sandwich element with thin face sheets. In such cases local indentation problem occur during bending and reliable shear strength is quite difficult to obtain. In such a case, performing either shear tests or by forcing the sandwich specimen to predominantly fail by shear under bending as suggested by Feldhusen et. al [10] could overcome the problem.

Until now, it has been discussed how to determine the strength of the foam core and the strength at the face-core interface with simple reliable test methods. It is also equally important to consider the strength of the face sheets as well. Typical face sheets used for sandwich design are made of metals and fibre reinforced plastics (FRP). The material data for metallic materials is well known and requires hardly tests to determine them. However there is a need for determining the necessary properties of FRP laminates. Since many commercial manufacturers are in a position to provide these data, additional material tests may not be usually necessary. Therefore it can be concluded that, with merely 3-4 tests, it is possible to provide the necessary strength data for the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion. Since, the strength data from tensile or shear tests implicitly contains the information regarding the mode of failure (core failure or face-core interface failure), the assignment of these strength values in a *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion for core materials would also implicitly represent the appropriate failure mode of sandwich materials. Hence the load carrying capacity of a sandwich structure can be determined. It shall be noted that the necessary linear elastic parameters for finite element simulations can also be obtained by performing these experiments.

VERIFICATION

This section validates the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion for foam core materials based on PMI as well as PUR.

Validation using Polymethacrylimide foams (PMI)

Evonik Röhm GmbH has developed a new 3-D failure criterion in collaboration with the German Institute for Polymers (DKI) for foam cores based on PMI, considering the influence of hydrostatic stress effects [5]. Description of this criterion is provided in this paper just for comparison with the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion. For a detailed description of this newly developed criterion, the interested reader is referred to literatures [5-6]. The failure potential of the newly developed criterion is given by:

$$\Phi = \frac{3.I_2' + a_1.\sigma_v.I_1 + a_2.I_1^2}{1 + a_1 + a_2} = \sigma_v^2 \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Where I_1 and I_2 are the first invariant and the secondary deviatoric invariant of the 3-D stress tensor respectively and σ_v is the equivalent stress. The constants a_1 and a_2 are described as the functions of the pure compressive, shear and tensile strengths of the foam core. The developed model is able to describe the strength differential effect of the PMI based foams Rohacell[®]. The validation of this criterion has been performed under combined tension/shear and compression/shear stress states, which has shown that the criterion is able to describe the failure envelope quite well.

In order to validate the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion for PMI based materials, this criterion is also described in the combined tension/shear and compression/shear states as follows:

$$\frac{1}{F_{1d}F_{1z}}(\sigma_1^2) + \left(\frac{1}{F_{1z}} - \frac{1}{F_{1d}}\right)(\sigma_1) + \frac{\tau^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

Figure 2: Verification of simplified Tsai-Wu criterion for Rohacell[®] 200 WF foams

Under this condition, the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion matches exactly the newly developed Rohacell[®] failure criterion. So all the tests performed in [5] using different materials i.e., Rohacell[®] 51 WF, Rohacell[®] 110 WF and Rohacell[®] 200 WF also satisfies the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion quite well. Figure 2 illustrates the applicability of the *simplified Tsai-Wu* failure criterion for Rohacell[®] 200 WF, a PMI-based polymer.

However, in a 3-D stress state there is a difference between the Rohacell[®] criterion and the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion. To explain this, the Rohacell[®] criterion for a biaxial stress state is given as follows:

$$\frac{1}{F_{1d}F_{1z}}(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) + \left(\frac{1}{F_{1z}} - \frac{1}{F_{1d}}\right)(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) - \sigma_1\sigma_2\left(\frac{1}{S^2} - \frac{2}{F_{1z}F_{1d}}\right) + \frac{\tau^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

By comparing Eq. 10 and Eq. 13, it is obvious that the only difference between these criteria lies in the description of the coefficient term for “ $\sigma_1\sigma_2$ ”. It shall be noted that this coefficient term is nothing but the interactive coefficient F_{12} as described in Eq. 2. Both criteria have their own assumptions in describing this interactive coefficient and hence only through performance of further experiments under complex loading state, the most suitable criterion for PMI foams could be found out. In any case, the Tsai-Wu criterion will describe the failure envelope of PMI foams better, because an additional experimental effort (for instance using biaxial tests) to find the coefficient F_{12} will completely eliminate any room for assumptions.

Validation using Polyurethane foams (PUR)

Experiments have been carried out at the Chair and Institute for Engineering Design (IKT) with PUR foam core sandwich beams in order to understand the failure mechanism as well as to force the sandwich beam to predominantly fail under shear in bending tests. The bending test set up and the basic specimen dimensions in millimetres are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Bending test set up

Several bending tests have been carried out, where the specimen dimensions have been changed in several configurations by bonding simple reinforcing plates at the line of transmission of forces to avoid local face wrinkling or compression failure of the foam core. The failure load, the thickness of the reinforcing plates, symmetry configuration and the modes of failure are given in the following table.

Table 1: Four point bending tests

Tests	Load during failure (kN)	Configuration	Thickness of reinforcing plates	Mode of failure
B1	2.9		-	Local failure

B2	3		-	Local failure
B3	5.2		1 mm	Shear failure
B4	5.5		1.5 mm	Shear failure
B5	6.4		2 mm	Shear failure
B6	6.5		2 mm	Shear failure
B7	6.7		2 mm	Shear failure
B8	5.9		2 plates of different lengths with the thickness of 1 mm each	Shear as well as local failure [10]

After completion of these tests, compression tests of four specimens were also performed according to DIN 53291. A typical load-displacement curve of this sandwich specimen under quasi-static compression tests is shown in figure 4. The average compressive strength of the foam core material is calculated to be approximately 0.34 Mpa. The shear strength of this foam core material as suggested by Feldhusen et al. [11] is approximately 0.29 Mpa. With in the framework of this paper, tensile tests have not been performed. In order to verify the applicability of Tsai-Wu criterion, Eq. 10 has been further modified by assuming that the tensile strength of the foam material equals its compression strength and is given as follows:

$$\frac{1}{F_{1d}^2}(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 - \sigma_1\sigma_2) + \frac{\tau^2}{S^2} = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

For each loading configuration, shown in Table 1, 2D- numerical simulations of the sandwich beam have been carried out to measure both the compressive and shear tensor components at the closer vicinity of the region of failure. These components along with the failure criterion (Eq. 14) in the combined compression/shear states are illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Typical load displacement curve of the PUR foam

Figure 5: Verification of simplified Tsai-Wu criterion for PUR based foams

CONCLUSION

This research shows that the simplified or modified Tsai-Wu failure criterion is well suitable to describe the failure envelope of high performance foams such as PMI as well as “secondary foams” such as PUR. Other important commercially available closed cell cellular foams for sandwich constructions include: the so called “linear” polyvinylchloride foams (L-PVC), cross-linked PVC foams, fire resistant polyisocyanurate foams (PIR), polystyrene foams (PS), styrene-acrylonitrile foams (SAN), polyetherimide foams (PEI) and polyethylene terephthalate foams (PET). The strength of these foams falls in to one of the following categories: high performance foams, “secondary” foams or a third category that compromises their strength differences. Since all these foams possess a similar macroscopic structure, it can be hypothesized that the Tsai-Wu criterion is also quite adequate to describe their failure envelope. If the strength properties of other axes (2 and 3) are suspected to be critical, then the *simplified Tsai-Wu* criterion can be modified accordingly, based on the theoretical background presented in this paper.

By employing the proposed methods, the overall modelling and experimental effort in dimensioning sandwich materials can be reduced considerably. The proposed experiments also enable good usage of materials and therefore do not compromise the light weight advantage.

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